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ABSTRACTS

exstrophy closures, and 21 months for re-operative closure. One patient had pin-site infection and had to remove pins earlier. The patient required further re-operative closure with osteotomy. The mean (range) percent approximation of the pubic rami was 63 (50-77).

Conclusions: This osteotomy procedure is useful in initial or repeat closure of cloacal exstrophy.

P 35. Treating multiple fractures of the humerus with Ilizarov apparatus

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Abstract Body : Aim: Is the evaluation of postoperative results of multiple closed fractures of the humeral diaphysis (taking into consideration segmental and open fractures) using the transosseous osteosynthesis with the Ilizarov apparatus.

Material and methods: In Clinic for orthopedic surgery and traumatology in Novi Sad, in period from 2005 to 2012, 35 patients with various types of humeral fractures were treated. Of that number, 30 of them (86%) had closed fractures (5 segmental and 25 multiple) while 5 patients (14%) had open fractures (2 Gustilo-Anderson two type I and 3 Gustilo-Anderson type II).

Average age was 40. Right upper arm fractures were present in 25 patients (71%), fractures of the left in 10 patients (29%). Average wearing of the apparatus was 4 months (3-5).

Results: Full recovery was obtained in 30 patients (86%). We have extended recovery in 3 patients (8%), pseudarthrosis in two patients (6%). Further complications were noted: in 5 pin-site infections, which have been successfully treated with antibiotics and frequent bandaging, 3 transient radial nerve lesions, a transient outage of sensitive functions of ulnar nerve and one iatrogenic pseudoaneurysm of brachial artery. To present our functional results we used Stewart-Hundley scale and based on it we had 28 excellent, 5 good and two bad results.

Conclusion: Treatment of multiple fractures of the upper arm diaphysis, including segmental and open fractures, using transosseous osteosynthesis with the Ilizarov apparatus, is by observations of the authors, the sovereign method or. the method of choice.

P 36. Two different size rings (200 and 180) were useful for the management of the distal tibial complex fracture. A case report.

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The Ilizarov external fixation system is useful in the management of the distal tibial fracture. But the reduction of the fracture fragments is sometimes difficult in the distal tibial complex fracture. I will represent the usefulness of two different size rings for the reduction of fracture fragments.

A patient was 15 years-old boy. He had a distal tibial fracture of his right leg. His fracture was managed by the Ilizarov external fixator. Two proximal tibial full rings (180) and 2 foot half rings (200) were applied, and both rings were connected by the telescopic rods. His fracture area was distracted using the